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WAYS TO PREVENT NEGATIVE DISORDERS IN SCHIZOPHRENIA

Abstract: In modern psychopathology, high cognitive, emotional and psychological dysfunction to negative symptoms of schizophrenia is one of the problems of dorzarb. At the same time, negative symptoms remain constant and an integral part of schizophrenia. This requires further improvement in ways to prevent negative disorders in schizophrenia

Key words: Schizophrenia, negative disorder, psychopathology, cognitive function

Introduction: The share of negative disorders in all major types of schizophrenia (fur-like, recurrent, continuous, excluding paranoid) is 29-40% [1-3]. The problem of negative disorders in schizophrenia and schizophrenic spectrum disorders is insufficiently studied [3-6].

Modern psychopathology of negative disorders is based on a long historical experience, laid down in the prenosological period [7-10]. According to J. Jackson, negative symptoms reflect the "loss" of reflexes at the level of higher cognitive, emotional and psychological functions, while positive ones represent a "phenomenon of release" (i.e. they are secondary to primary - negative disorders - AS) and only distort or hyperbolize normal functioning [11-16].

At the same time, negative symptoms are persistent and persist in 20-40% after the first episode of schizophrenia [17-21], and in 16-35% - within a year after its passing [22-27] and in 35% - even 2 years after the first hospitalization. Another argument is the incompleteness of the clinical analysis of the schizophrenic defect, despite the understanding of negative symptoms as a "key domain of the psychopathology of schizophrenia" [28-34].

Thus, the conditions that formed the subject of this study can be rightfully attributed to the space of deficit disorders conceptualized in a number of modern publications within the framework of negative schizophrenia [35-42].

The purpose of the study. To carry out a conceptual analysis of negative disorders in schizophrenia and schizophrenic spectrum diseases.

The results of the study. The results of the study indicate that this distribution is not accidental, but obeys the dichotomy of the basic symptoms of "common syndromes". Although, according to the psychometric assessment, the structure of each of the general syndromes under consideration presents both a volitional defect - abulia with the phenomenon of dependence, and an emotional defect, i.e. both components reflecting the dichotomous structure of the schizophrenic defect, the distribution of these patterns of negative disorders in the clinical space of general syndromes is uneven.

The analysis of the casuistry at our disposal allows us (as already mentioned above) to assume that the ranking of psychopath-like disorders in accordance with the dichotomy of the basic defect is possible (and feasible) not only within one single cluster of RL, but acquires a more universal character and is valid for the distribution of all psychopath-like disorders regardless of the cluster of RL to which they belong.

The general structure of deficit changes by the type of volitional defect, extrapolated to all the syndromes of the defensive pole that represent it, is characterized by a gross decrease in psychophysical endurance (when overlapping volitional disorders with asthenic symptoms) and/or volitional regulation of mental activity (apathy-abulia according to SANS - 4.3 ± 0.7 points; volitional disorders according to PANSS - 5.1 ± 0.3 points; asthenia according to MFI-20 - 77 ± 15.3 points), with an increase in passivity, listlessness and indecision, the addition of features of asthenic autism and dependence on a narrow circle of significant others (decreased sociability according to PANSS - 3.5 ± 0.5 points; lack of close friends according to SPQ-A - 5.6 ± 0.4 points; relationships with colleagues and loved ones according to SANS - 3.2 ± 0.2 points; excessive social anxiety according to SPQ-A - 6.2 ± 1.3 points; passive social self-isolation according to PANSS - 5.2 ± 0.4 points; interpersonal anxiety according to SCL-90-R - 1.5 ± 0.3 points; $p \leq 0.01$).

Emotional disorders in this group are expressed to a non-negligible degree and reflect the impoverishment of the general level of social activity (associated primarily with asthenic symptoms, sharply pointed reflexive mechanisms, as well as the tendency of patients to form

sensitive ideas of attitude) and the narrowing of the range of emotional attachments to the boundaries of symbiotic ties with relatives or spouses (anhedonia-asociality according to SANS - 3.0 ± 0.2 points, flattened affect according to SPQ-A - 3.7 ± 0.4 points).

The structure of deficit changes, which is uniform for all "common syndromes" of the expansive pole (with a picture of an emotional type defect), differs on a statistically significant basis (as opposed to deficit disorders of the volitional type) by maintaining a general psychophysical pressure, in which the phenomena of energy potential reduction are manifested not by a decrease in the level of mental energy, but by its distortion in the form of chaotic, purposeless and volitional control of activity.

This is especially evident when comparing the characteristics of the labor status of patients with the indicators of the scales of apatoabulic changes (apathy -abulia according to SANS - 3.6 ± 0.3 points; volitional disorders according to PANSS - 2.7 ± 1.2 points; asthenia according to MFI-20-25 ± 11.2 points).

Pronounced changes in emotionality proper (anhedonia-asociality according to SANS - 4.3 ± 0.2 points, flattened affect according to SPQ-A - 6.8 ± 0.4 points) come to the fore, common for the entire group of negative emotional disorders, manifested by its gross impoverishment with the formation of regressive syntonicity traits, loss of the ability to empathy and the formation of deep emotional attachments, pathological sharpening of the features of rationalism, egocentricity and pragmatism (absence of close friends according to SPQ-A - 8.3 ± 0.4 points; decrease in sociability according to PANSS - 5.1 ± 1.2 points; relationships with colleagues and relatives according to SANS - 4.5 ± 0.3 points; eccentric behavior according to SPQ-A - 5.7 ± 1.8 points; excessive social anxiety (SPQ-A) - 0.9 ± 0.2 points; interpersonal anxiety according to SCL-90 - 0.2 ± 0.5 points; hostility according to SCL-90 - 1.9 ± 0.3 points).

It has been established that psychopathological manifestations of the defect in schizophrenic spectrum disorders are represented by deficient symptom complexes of the psychopathic register (psychopath-like disorders), are of a limited (circumscriptional) nature, have a monosyndromic structure, are detected already at the level of prodromal disorders and are associated with premorbid pathoharacterological dimensions. The trajectory of negative

disorders in schizophrenic spectrum disorders characterized by limited proгредиency is determined - ending at the prodromal stage with either a prodromal or a phase course. Aspects of psychopharmacotherapy of negative disorders with drugs of modern generations are also discussed.

Conclusion. Thus, psychopathic symptom complexes acting in the space of "general syndromes" can be qualified as secondary to basic deficiency disorders. Accordingly, the allocation of a psychopath-like defect as a syndromic (ordained by others) form of negative disorders, according to our research, seems unlawful.

References:

1. Allambergenov A. J. et al. Postcovid syndrome and its neuropsychiatric consequences after covid-19 in patients with alcoholism //European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. – 2023. – T. 11. – C. 42-46.
2. Ochilov U. U., Turaev B. T., Zhumageldiev N. N. Peculiarities of the formation and course of alcoholism in persons with character accentuations and personality disorders //Bulletin of Science and Education. – 2020. – №. 10-4. – C. 88.
3. Temirpulatovich T. B. Depressive disorders in alcohol recipients and its socio-economic consequences during the covid-19 pandemic //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2023. – T. 4. – №. 1. – C. 162-168.
4. Temirpulatovich T. B. et al. Clinical Manifestations of Suicidal Behaviors as a Result of Depressive Disorders During Adolescence //Eurasian Medical Research Periodical. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 55-58.
5. Temirpulatovich T. B. Sexual behavioral disorders after the covid-19 pandemic in patients with alcoholism //World Bulletin of Public Health. – 2022. – T. 10. – C. 207-209.
6. Temirpulatovich T. B., Hamidullayevna X. D. Neuropsychiatric disorders that develop in a complication of covid-19 to alcoholism //European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. – 2023. – T. 11. – C. 47-51.
7. Temirpulatovich T. B., Murodullayevich K. R., Uzokboyevich T. A. The Interrelationship of The Covid-19 Pandemic with Alcohol Abuse //Eurasian Medical Research Periodical. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 137-139.

8. Temirpulatovich T. B., Sabrievna V. A. Effects of the Covid-19 Pandemic on the Frequency of Alcohol Abuse and Clinical and Psychopathological Features //Eurasian Medical Research Periodical. – 2022. – Т. 8. – С. 68-71.
9. Temirpulatovich T. B., Uzokboyevich T. A. Effects of exogenous psychological effects on alcohol consumption during the covid-19 pandemic //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 1. – С. 157-161.
10. Temirpulotovich T. B. et al. The Impact Of Medical And Social Factors On Alcohol Abuse In Patients With Alcoholism During The Covid-19 Pandemic //Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results. – 2022. – С. 8195-8200.
11. Turaev B. the course of the disease during the covid-19 pandemic in patients with alcoholism //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D8. – С. 130-134.
12. Turaev B., Velilyaeva A. Formation and course of alcoholism in young women with alcoholic psychosis //Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 226-232.
13. Usmanovich O. U. et al. Detection of adrenaline and stress conditions in patients using psychoactive substances with hiv infection //CUTTING EDGESCIENCE. – 2020. – С. 42.
14. Очилов У. У. и др. Диагностические особенности у пациентов с эндогенными психическими заболеваниями //Проблемы современной науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 10 (155). – С. 50-52.
15. Очилов У. У. и др. Клинические особенности психопатического поведения у подростков с психическими расстройствами //Вестник науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 23-3 (101). – С. 71-74.
16. Очилов У. У. и др. Оптимизация профилактики когнитивных и депрессивных расстройств при алкоголизме //Вестник науки и образования. – 2022. – №. 1-1 (121). – С. 109-113.
17. Очилов У. У. и др. Проблемы современной науки и образования //проблемы современной науки и образования Учредители: Олимп. – №. 1. – С. 64-67.

17. Очилов У. У. и др. Эндогенный психоз и расстройства шизофренического спектра в позднем возрасте //Проблемы современной науки и образования. – 2022. – №. 1 (170). – С. 64-67.
19. Очилов У. У., Тураев Б. Т., Жумагелдиев Н. Н. Особенности формирования и течения алкоголизма у лиц с акцентуациями характера и личностными расстройствами //Вестник науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 10-4 (88). – С. 101-103.
20. Очилов У. У., Тураев Б. Т., Жумагелдиев Н. Н. Особенности формирования и течения алкоголизма у лиц с акцентуациями характера и личностными расстройствами //Вестник науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 10-4 (88). – С. 101-103.
21. Очилов У. У., Тураев Б. Т., Хушвактова Д. Х. Распространенность когнитивных нарушений у пациентов с алкоголизмом //Вестник науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 17-2 (95). – С. 104-106.
22. Очилов У., Тураев Б., Алкаров Р. Клинические особенности депрессивных расстройств у подростков //Журнал вестник врача. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 75-77.
23. Очилов У., Тураев Б., Алкаров Р. Ўсмирларда депрессив бузилишларнинг клиник хусусиятлари //Журнал вестник врача. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 75-77.
24. Тураев Б. и др. Алкоголизм билан касалланган беморларда депрессив бузилишларнинг клиник ва психопатологик хусусиятларини ўрганиш //Журнал вестник врача. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 92-94.
25. Тураев Б. Т. и др. Covid-19 pandemiyasi davrida ruhiy omillarning spirtli ichimliklarni iste'mol qilishga ta'siri //Журнал биомедицины и практики. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 3.
26. Тураев Б. Т. и др. Covid-19 pandemiyasi vaqtida spirtli ichimliklarni iste'mol qiluvchi shaxslarda depressiv buzilishlarning tarqalishi //Журнал биомедицины и практики. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 1.
27. Тураев Б. Т. и др. Диагностика и лечение коморбидности алкоголизма и депрессивных расстройств //Вестник науки и образования. – 2021. – №. 4-2 (107). – С. 26-30.

28. Тураев Б. Т. Личностные нозогенные реакции больных с дерматологическими заболеваниями //Актуальные проблемы нейробиологии психических и аддиктивных расстройств. Томск. – 2020. – С. 157-159.
29. Тураев Б. Т. Маиший ичкиликбозлик муаммоси бўлган шахсларга ижтимоий омилларнинг covid-19 пандемиси даврида таъсири //Журнал биомедицины и практики. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 4.
30. Тураев Б. Т., Жабборов Х. Х., Жумагелдиев Н. Н. Гендерные различия депрессивной симптоматики у больных параноидной шизофренией //Volgamedscience. – 2021. – С. 459-460.
31. Тураев Б. Т., Икромова П. Х., Жабборов Х. Х. Тревожно-депрессивные расстройства в период беременности //Volgamedscience. – 2021. – С. 460-461.
32. Тураев Б. Т., Очиллов У. У., Алкаров Р. Б. Socio-demographic characteristics of somatized depression //Новый день в медицине. – 2020. – №. 2. – С. 231-233.
33. Тураев Б. Т., Очиллов У. У., Икромова П. Х. Частота и структура неврологических нарушений у больных подросткового возраста с психическими расстройствами //Volgamedscience. – 2021. – С. 462-463.
34. Тураев Б. Т., Очиллов У. У., Кубаев Р. М. Распределение тревоги и депрессии при аффективных расстройствах соматизированной депрессии //Medicus. – 2020. – №. 3. – С. 58-60.
35. Тураев Б. Т., Очиллов У. У., Хаятов Р. Б. Клинические особенности премобидного течения депрессивных расстройств и алкогольной зависимости //Эндогенные психические расстройства. – 2020. – С. 64-68.
36. Тураев Б. Т., Хаятов Р. Б. Апатия в структуре депрессии позднего возраста //Молодежь и медицинская наука в XXI веке. – 2019. – С. 293-293.
37. Тураев Б. Т., Хаятов Р. Б. Особенности электроэнцефалографических показателей у больных алкогольной зависимостью //Актуальные проблемы психиатрии и наркологии в современных условиях. – 2019. – С. 150-151.

38. Тураев Б. Т., Хаятов Р. Б. Преморбидные особенности личности и суицидальное поведение больных алкоголизмом позднего возраста //Актуальные проблемы психиатрии и наркологии в современных условиях. – 2019. – С. 151-153.
39. Тураев Б. Т., Хаятов Р. Б. Различия в поведенческих нарушениях и злоупотребления спиртными напитками в катamnестическом исследовании лиц с расстройствами зрелой личности //Антология российской психотерапии и психологии. – 2019. – С. 171-171.
40. Тураев Б., Хаятов Р. Рекуррент ҳамда биполяр типдаги депрессиялардаги аффектив бузилишлар соматизацияланишиниг клиник психопатологик хусусиятлари //Журнал вестник врача. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 95-99.
41. Тураев Б., Хаятов Р. Суицидальные намерения у лиц с синдромом алкогольной зависимости при наличии депрессивных расстройств //Журнал вестник врача. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 115-117.
42. Хаятов Р. Б. и др. Аффективные расстройства у больных алкогольной зависимостью как фактор риска развития суицидального поведения //Достижения науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 11 (52). – С. 96-98.
43. Farrukh S. TREATMENT OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION AND FIRST AID." science and Innovation //International Scientific Journal. ISSN. – 2022. – С. 2181-3337.
44. og'li Shernazarov F. F. CONGENITAL HEART DISEASE-CAUSES, CLASSIFICATION, DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT, COMPLICATIONS, CONSEQUENCES //Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 84-89.
45. Shernazarov F. ATHEROSCLEROSIS: CAUSES, SYMPTOMS, DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND PREVENTION //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D5. – С. 7-12.
46. Farrukh S. TREATMENT OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION AND FIRST AID //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D3. – С. 317-320.
47. Shernazarov F., TYPES OF HEMORRHAGIC DISEASES, CHANGES IN NEWBOENS, THEIR EARLY DIAGNOSIS. – 2022.

48. Ш. и др. ПУТИ УСТРАНЕНИЯ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D3. – С. 313-316.
49. Farrux S. The Structure of the Heart and its Physiology in Regular Athletes //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – Т. 8. – С. 102-105.
50. Shernazarov F. ATHEROSCLEROSIS: CAUSES, SYMPTOMS, DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND PREVENTION //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D5. – С. 7-12.
51. ДИАБЕТА П. У. С. То^ ирова Жайрона Иззатилло^ изи //Шерназаров Фаррух «Science and innovation. – 2022. – С. 313-316.
52. Farrukh S. TREATMENT OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION AND FIRST AID." science and Innovation" International Scientific Journal. ISSN: 2181-3337, 1 (3), 317-320. – 2022.
53. Farkhod og'li, Shernazarov Farrukh. "CONGENITAL HEART DISEASE-CAUSES, CLASSIFICATION, DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT, COMPLICATIONS, CONSEQUENCES. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES, 2 (3), 84-89." (2022).
- 54 Farrux S. Eurasian Scientific Herald PENACCESS //PEERREVIEWEDJOURNAL <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/esh>. – Т. 8.
55. Farhod o'g'li S. F. GASTRIT—SABABLARI, ALOMATLARI, TASHXISLASH, DAVOLASH, DORILAR, ASORATLARI, OLDINI OLISH. The Best Innovator in Science, 1 (1), 103-107. – 2022.
56. Shernazarov F. et al. SYMPTOMS, APPEARANCE, TREATMENT OF VARICOSE VEINS. – 2022.
57. Farrukh S. TREATMENT OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION AND FIRST AID." science and Innovation //International Scientific Journal. ISSN. – 2022. – С. 2181-3337.
58. Shernazarov F. F. CONGENITAL HEART DISEASE-CAUSES, CLASSIFICATION, DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT, COMPLICATIONS, CONSEQUENCES //Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 84-89.

